

Preliminary clinical investigation on fluoride contamination in Nalhati subdivision (West Bengal); possible structural changes of water due to fluoride ion and related clinical aspects

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Abstract : Fluorosis is widely prevalent in Nalhati in Bhirbhum District. Attempts were made for a preliminary study on the clinical aspects of fluorosis in fluoride affected victims in Nalhati. Though the tap water is relatively free from fluoride contamination but fluoride concentrations in urine were found to be appreciably high. The victims suffered abnormally high alkaline phosphatase and high values of AST (GOT) but low calcium levels in serum leading to calcium loss, renal insufficiency, vitamin D deficiency and bone diseases of low to severe magnitudes. Efforts have been made to throw light on structural changes of water due to fluoride contamination and other related aspects.

Keywords : Clinical aspects, fluoride contamination, ion chromatography, Nalhati (West Bengal), structural changes of water.

Introduction

Water is the lifeline of all the activities associated with living being in human, animal, and plant kingdom. But the quality of water (both surface and ground water) is widely variable due to variable geochemical and environmental (domestic and industrial) reasons in the different parts of the world^{1,2}. The quality of water in most part of the world is affected due to natural and anthropogenic reasons. In recent years, there are reports of increased fluoride levels in water (especially in underground water) and water related substances like food, tea, meat etc.

Fluorine or fluoride (F⁻) ion is classified as toxic element causing fluorosis beyond a certain limit (1.5 mg/L, WHO standard) in water and human body³. Endemic dental and skeletal fluorosis associated with non-skeletal manifestations like neurological disorder, gastro-intestinal complaints like loss of appetite, constipation, muscular pain are wide spread in India⁴⁻⁷, China, Africa and other parts of the world due to ingestion of fluoridated water. In India, 17 out of 29 states are affected greatly from fluo-

rosis, the worst affected states are Gujarat and Rajasthan followed by Andhra Pradesh (undivided), Haryana, Punjab, Karnataka, Maharashtra and Jharkhand⁷.

In this connection, it is desirable to highlight the reasons of fluorosis and F contamination in ground water, biochemical and clinical aspects of ingestion of F by patients and experiments using male albino and in rabbits. Sources of F contamination :

- (1) Disintegration and mineralization of F bearing rocks.
- (2) Anthropogenic pollution arising from the increasing use of cryolite for steel and Al manufacture and for processing fluorapatite for the manufacture of phosphate fertilizers and pesticides.
- (3) Movement of elemental particles and pollutants and seeping of contaminants in underground aquifers.

However, occupational health hazards though not considered properly from quarrying and cutting of stones (containing sufficient amount of F) of different varieties,

shaping, and polishing for decorative or other purposes of building temples, mosques etc. are the sources of airborne F in the form of particulate F particles. Unfortunately, it is impossible to stop F contamination of water from the anthropogenic sources outlined before for reasons well known. Some of the findings due to high F intake are⁷⁻²⁴ :

- (i) Decrease in ionic serum and plasma Ca, secondary PTH (parathyroid hormone) and urinary creatinine, changes in mineral composition of human dentitions.
- (ii) Damages of brain tissues and reduction in IQ in children.
- (iii) Oxidative stress in animals and changes in animal behavior.
- (iv) Powerful influences on enzymes and endocrine gland functions that affect or control the status of oxidant/antioxidant levels in living systems.
- (v) Decrease *in vitro* fertility in males.

The studies also recommend the use of increased Ca, proteins, and vitamins as ameliorating measures against F affected patients.

Limited study of F contaminations in West Bengal²⁴⁻²⁶ showed that the F contamination is relatively less in West Bengal except in few pockets like Bhirbhum, Bankura, Purulia, and parts of Midnapore (East and West), and Bardwan districts. However, 4,545 square kilometer area of the Bhirbhum district (particularly Nalhati sub-division) with a population of more than 3 million has been reported to be worst affected area in West Bengal due to F contamination. It has been reported that one-seventh of the population have been suffering from dental or skeletal fluorosis or both due to excessive intake of F. Other abnormal effects (exacerbated by poor diets deficient in Ca and vitamins) are hardening and pain in bones, joints, osteoporosis, and neurological disorders.

But little systematic study on clinical examination of patients suffering from fluorosis due to intake of F contaminated water, animal, and food stuff had been made or reported.

The work is an attempt to have a preliminary examination of the biochemical parameters of patients suffering from fluorosis in Nalhati. The results had been properly

analyzed and ameliorating measures for F affected patients had been suggested based on scientific chemical knowledge and literature reports. Moreover, a simple and low cost remedial measure suitable for rural poor and for common people in F affected countries for removing F from fluoridated water had been put forward.

Materials and methods

- (a) Study area : Nalhati sub-division, Bhirbhum district.
- (b) Sources and collection of samples :
 - (i) 26 victims supposedly suffering from malnutrition and fluorosis (Table 1).
 - (ii) Tap water (recently introduced at the time of the experiment) (Table 1).
 - (iii) Blood samples in medicated vials.
 - (iv) Urine in clean, dry and pathogenically free test tubes used for collection of urine.

Experimental

The F concentration in the potable water and urine samples was measured using Ion Chromatography (IC). Multi-traceable standards from NIST were used for calibration and quantization of anions particularly the quantization of F in the present experiment. Precautions were made to ensure all solutions to be F free. The collected samples were filtered through Gelman make nylon membrane filter having 0.45 μm porosity and diameter 47 mm. 10 μL of the samples were used for F estimation. Urine samples were properly diluted with de-ionized water. As the concentrations of Cl^- ion were found to be much higher than F^- ion concentrations, suppression of peaks were observed and the solutions were appreciably diluted (1 : 25) for F estimation. Moreover, instead of determining the anions together, IC was standardized against standard solutions of F and only F concentrations were determined. All biochemical measurements were made as suggested in instrumental manuals and in our publications²⁴⁻²⁶. However, due to insufficient quantity of bloods and non-availability of F ion selective electrode at our disposal, F concentration in blood samples could not be determined.

Instruments

- (A) IC^{24,25,27} : Metrohm Ion Chromatography instrument with Metrosep A Supp 3 of length 250 mm,

ID 4.6 mm column was used in the present study. A buffer containing 1.7 mM Na₂CO₃, and 1.8 mM Na₂CO₃ was used as a mobile phase, the flow rate being 1.0 mL/min.

- (B) Electrolytes and biochemical measurements of the samples were taken using
- (i) Clinical parameters other than electrolytes were assayed Spectrophotometrically in Daytona, Randox (UK), Random Access Fully Automated Chemical Analyzer with commercial kits supplied by Randox (USA).
 - (ii) Electrolytes, e.g. sodium, potassium, chlorides were assayed with Ion Selective Electrodes in Easylyte, Medica (USA).

Table 1. Names of the victims, their sex, age and fluoride content in urine sample

Sl. No.	Victim's name	Sex (M/F)	Age (years)	F conc. in urine (mg/L)
1.	Nikhil Mondal	M	50	5.1
2.	Rikta Mondal	F	45	2.1
3.	Palit Mondal	M	17	2.5
4.	Vivakananda Mondal	M	55	3.2
5.	Hariranjana Mondal	M	45	1.7
6.	Sathi Mondal	F	15	3.1
7.	Dhananjay Rabidas	M	55	4.1
8.	Tamal Rabidas	M	55	0.8
9.	Dipak Let	M	18	1.6
10.	Haradhan Let	M	45	2.4
11.	Apsari Mondal	F	42	0.9
12.	Ajit Mondal	M	50	1.9
13.	Mamata Das	F	48	0.5
14.	Ananta Mondal	M	60	0.5
15.	Sabita Let	F	50	1.7
16.	Neuton Let	M	18	1.3
17.	Sadhan Mondal	M	55	0.3
18.	Samir Kumar Mondal	M	48	3.2
19.	Prabhat Chandra Mondal	M	31	2.3
20.	Mithun Let	M	35	2.1
21.	Mira Rani Foujdar	F	70	1.0
22.	Chandana Mondal	F	35	1.3
23.	Arnupurna Mondal	F	65	3.6
24.	Kamalesh Mondal	M	23	3.0
25.	Kailash Mondal	M	19	2.3
26.	Sanat Mondal	M	20	0.7

Results and discussion

The names of the victims, their sex, age, and fluoride content in urine sample are presented in Table 1. Results of the biochemical estimation of test serum samples collected from the victims of the affected areas are presented in Table 2. The average values of the determinants, their standard deviations and normal ranges are presented in Table 3. However, serum samples were not adequate to measure F ion using IC. Moreover, in view of the presence of other ions like Cl⁻ in appreciable quantities, measurement of F ion using F ion selective electrode or by Gas chromatography appears to be more appropriate at least for blood serum samples.

The lacunas for this experiment are :

- (i) Dug well or tube well water samples were not collected but patients in question were accustomed to use dug well tube well water though the tap water (collected) was introduced only recently.
- (ii) The F content in the tap water is relatively free from F contaminations (much below than WHO standard of 1.5 mg/L).
- (iii) The F ion concentrations in the blood serum appeared to be relatively low from preliminary investigation but could not be verified from IC measurements.

However, F concentrations in urine (Table 1) appeared to be abnormally high (much above 0.3 mg/L, the normal value of F in urine). The results though difficult to explain are not unexpected as the supply of tap water started in recent years and most of the water used was from dug wells and ponds²⁸. Moreover, the water for irrigation purposes contained appreciable concentrations of F ion and apparently vegetables and other items had been contaminated with F ion, otherwise such abnormal values of F ion in urine were not possible. The abnormalities are also manifested in the high alkaline phosphatase level, low calcium level in serum and high values of AST (GOT) [AST – aspartate trans aminylase, GOT – glutamine oxaloacetic acid trans aminylase]²⁹⁻³².

It is well known that brain, kidney and liver are usually affected by chronic fluorosis and may lead to changes in biochemical parameters in blood serum.

Natural concentration of F in water ranges from 0.01

Table 2. Results of biochemical estimation of serum samples

Sl. No.	ALK Phos. (µg/L)	Creatinine (mg/dL)	AST (GOT) (µg/dL)	Total protein (g/dL)	Albumin (g/dL)	K ⁺ (mM/L)	Cl ⁻ (mM/L)	Na ⁺ (mM/L)	Ca ²⁺ (mM/L)
1.	247.2	0.89	25.4	7.98	3.67	3.51	99	137	7.69
2.	185.1	0.76	22.3	7.52	3.89	3.49	97	133	7.79
3.	183.5	0.81	29.1	7.11	4.12	4.12	96	134	7.66
4.	191	1.14	38	7.79	4.34	4.8	94	132	7.69
5.	162	0.9	38.4	7.42	4.2	4.19	97	132	8.65
6.	204.9	0.71	35.6	8.54	4.61	3.9	98	136	5.07
7.	163	0.92	25.5	6.84	3.64	4.26	90	130	7.36
8.	178.5	0.26	27.1	6.98	4.2	4.41	101	139	8.8
9.	179.5	0.98	29.2	7.51	4.21	3.75	98	135	8.12
10.	207.6	0.91	23.2	7.61	3.99	3.91	96	131	5.75
11.	202.1	0.75	24.9	6.99	4.12	3.86	98	136	8.63
12.	169.9	0.9	29.9	7.27	4.16	4.3	96	134	7.98
13.	126.2	0.76	19.9	7.31	3.87	3.74	97	135	7.5
14.	164.1	0.86	21.9	6.63	3.35	3.49	91	129	9.16
15.	125.9	0.56	25	7.11	3.94	3.29	101	139	8.31
16.	155.2	0.78	32	6.98	4.07	3.87	97	132	7.65
17.	112.8	1.44	21	7.37	3.83	3.28	94	132	8.54
18.	207.1	0.94	35.5	7	4.16	4.73	100	135	7.57
19.	188.9	1.01	29.8	7.01	3.98	5.49	142	199	7.78
20.	113.2	0.71	26	7.48	4.25	3.82	96	132	7.19
21.	220.8	1.01	32.1	8.26	3.88	4.38	113	155	9.15
22.	190.5	0.98	27.8	6.98	4.01	4.7	117	160	8.21
23.	176.9	1.34	40.5	7.12	3.21	3.77	100	138	7.34
24.	188.4	0.89	34.2	7.45	3.78	5.11	127	176	7.76
25.	274.9	0.94	37.5	8.42	4.71	3.82	101	140	8.56
26.	145.3	0.92	26.9	6.78	3.32	3.83	102	145	8.45

to 10 ppm which appears to be limited by the solubility of fluorite (about 9 ppm in pure water), water high in Ca²⁺ content do not contain more than 1 ppm of F. Strong affinity of F⁻ for Ca²⁺ is capable of replacing other ions particularly phosphate from Ca-salts in bones, teeth etc. of the living systems to form insoluble CaF₂ (calcium fluorite). Moreover, water and Ca²⁺ are also distributed in different microscopic organs of the body system and the chronic fluorosis may cause disorder. F⁻ ion has the capability of displacing other anions like HCO₃⁻, H₂PO₄⁻, Cl⁻ etc. from respective counter ions including bio-molecules. Kosmotropic F⁻ ion can change ionic balance between the intra-cellular and extra-cellular fluids (ICF and ECF) leading to pressure related ailments.

The role of most important anomalous body fluid, water in fluorosis has been ignored. Water, due to its

anisotropicity, co-operativity, H-bonding ability, ability of self assembly, and directional properties interacts with the hydrophobic moieties like proteins, DNA, RNA etc. and orients them. In spite of advancement, all the miraculous properties of water and the properties of important biological compounds like proteins, nucleic acids etc. are not well understood. Water plays a crucial role in protein folding i.e. the process by which each protein, in spite of numerous folding configurations possible, always acquires or reverts to a functionally effective unique three dimensional shape. Hydrophobic interactions and H-bonding between water and protein molecules are supposed to be the main driving forces in protein folding. As a result, proteins (or other bio-molecules) fold, assume shape, assemble etc. DNA forms helices and able to zip or unzip, enzymes possess their 3D structures and bio-catalytic ac-

Table 3. Result evaluation of biochemical estimations

Sl. No.	Estimation type	Average value	Standard deviation	Normal range
1.	ALK Phos. (µg/L)	179.4	37.1	40–125
2.	Creatinine (mg/dL)	0.89	0.22	0.6–1.2
3.	AST (GOT) (µg/dL)	29.2	5.9	8–20
4.	Total protein (g/dL)	7.36	0.50	6.0–8.3
5.	Albumin (g/dL)	3.98	0.35	3.5–5.0
6.	K ⁺ (mM/L)	4.07	0.55	4.0–4.7
7.	Cl ⁻ (mM/L)	101.5	11.4	96–106
8.	Na ⁺ (mM/L)	140.6	15.9	135–145
9.	Ca²⁺ (mM/L)	7.86	0.91	9.0–10.5
10.	F in urine	2.0	1.2	0.3

tivities due to H-bonding abilities and collective behavior of water molecules^{33–37}.

However, (i) F with high H-bonding ability (much greater than oxygen) may directly interact with the atoms of proteins and bio-molecules and destroys or affects their structure or activities. (ii) F destroys the essential 3D water structures, destroys the self assembly, distorts or destructs the 3D structures of proteins and enzymes. F may also affect hydrophobic interactions. These may cause destruction or denaturation of protein molecules.

It is clear that the combined effects of strong affinity of F⁻ for Ca²⁺ ion and strong H-bonding capability of F⁻ lead to Ca²⁺ loss and structure destruction of water and bio-molecules including proteins, DNA etc. These are responsible for all subsequent effects like low Ca²⁺ ion level (may be the reasons of renal insufficiency, vitamin D deficiency, hypoparathyroidism), high values of alkaline phosphatase (mainly due to bone diseases like physiologic bone growth, osteomalacia, osteogenic sarcoma, bone metastases and a host of other diseases), high values of AST (GOT) (due to its release in the blood stream arising from tissue damage)^{33–37}.

The reasons for increased F concentration in water and indirectly in foods and animals cannot be changed or they are beyond rectification as the reasons for pollution will go unabated with increased population and industrialization and lack of adequate surface water with low F content. However adverse affects of F can be eliminated with Ca, protein and vitamin supplements in moderate amounts without no adverse affects or health risk.

It is desirable to have F free water but the practical feasibility of supplying F free water to common people appears to be remote in a country with large population without environmental awareness and financial constraints and lack of adequate quality of surface water. However, taking water mixed with slight amount of lime water, use of betel rolls with slacked lime and cardamom without areca nut, use of little clear lime water, use of mask to prevent airborne particulates in body systems through inhalation or by mouth may be helpful. Fluoridated water may be purified using indigenous method as one given below.

Water from dug well or ponds should be taken in a tank (with outlets) containing sufficient amount of soil with adequate amount of lateral soil and slight powdered lime stone and KMnO₄ and shaken thoroughly and allowed to settle. The tank should be covered to avoid dust and other impurities, though sunlight and air is beneficial. Decanted water relatively free from As and F can be used for cooking and other purposes.

For drinking purposes, treated water is allowed to trickle through beds of sand, charcoal, and pebbles or stone chips taken in a porous earthenware pots with outlet to collect the filtered water. The water can be taken as such or with disinfectants if necessary.

However, our works are inadequate to throw light on fluorosis in West Bengal and India at large. Extensive work is needed to assess the severity of fluorosis in India by proper monitoring the water quality and the measures to be taken for its amelioration.

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